

Analyzing the Relationship Between Gas Consumption and Airborne Pollutants: Case Study of Zagreb, Croatia

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Abstract

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and metals in particulate matter significantly contribute to the health risks associated with air pollution. Hence, their measurements and source apportionment are relevant. This paper comprehensively analyzes the relationship between gas consumption and PAHs and metals in the PM₁₀ fraction of particulate matter. The study investigates the potential associations using statistical techniques and quantifies the relationship between gas consumption patterns, meteorological conditions, and the measured concentrations of PAHs and metals in the atmosphere. The statistical methods comprise correlation analysis, Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), and linear regression. NMF analysis was employed to understand relationships among variables and potential sources of pollutants. NMF results revealed seasonal influences and different sources of pollutants in the studied area. PAHs with four aromatic rings have been grouped separately from 5- and 6-ring PAHs, suggesting two distinct sources of pollution – heating and traffic emissions. Metals such as As, Pb, Zn, and Cd are grouped, indicating mixed anthropogenic sources. The separation of Mn, Fe, and Cu in a distinguished group signifies their distinct origin, probably non-combustion traffic emissions (vehicle parts wearing).

1. Introduction

Air pollution is an enduring and pressing global concern with profound implications for human health. It can cause or contribute to increased mortality or severe illness or pose a present or potential hazard to human health (Kampa & Castanas, 2008; Poulsen et al., 2023; Sørensen et al., 2022). Among the various pollutants that contribute to this issue, particulate matter (PM) is one of the primary and concerning components of health (Anderson et al., 2012; Goshua et al., 2022; Pritchett et al., 2022), consisting of solid particles or liquid droplets suspended in the air from many natural and human-induced sources (Karagulian et al., 2015). The composition of PM is diverse, as it can absorb and transport a variety of pollutants. However, its main components include metals, organic compounds, materials of biological origin, ions, reactive gases, etc. (Kampa & Castanas, 2008; Pöschl, 2005). It is a well-established fact that pollutant concentrations in the air of central and south-eastern Europe tend to increase during the winter season due to heightened emissions associated with heating sources, reaching levels that could pose a risk to human health (Cao et al., 2009; Cvetković et al., 2015; Huang & Wang, 2014; Pehneć et al., 2020; Siudek & Frankowski, 2018). This observation underscores the significance of investigating the correlation between gas consumption as a heating surrogate variable, meteorological parameters (mainly temperature), and pollutant levels (Akyüz & Çabuk, 2009). Employing statistical techniques, including source apportionment, facilitates exploring these relationships (Bi et al., 2007; Thurston et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2020).

Within the context of airborne PM, a specific subgroup enriched with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) emerges as a focal point of scientific interest and environmental concern (Mallah et al., 2022; Rogula-Kozłowska et al., 2013; A. Singh et al., 2023). PAHs are organic compounds composed of multiple condensed aromatic rings, often originating from incomplete combustion processes (Krzyszczak & Czech, 2021; Ren et al., 2017). These compounds have garnered considerable attention due to their potential for adverse health effects and environmental impact (Abdel-Shafy & Mansour, 2016; Jakovljević et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2013; Mahasakpan et al., 2023). They are often encountered in various environmental matrices, including soil, water, sediment, and even food, reflecting their widespread distribution in nature (Barathi et al., 2023; X.-T. Wang et al., 2013). PAHs can find their way into the environment through many pathways, mainly arising from anthropogenic activities such as the combustion of fossil fuels, wood or organic materials, industrial processes, or agricultural activities. (Dat & Chang, 2017; Liang et al., 2006; S. Singh et al., 2022). Natural sources, including wildfires and volcanic eruptions, also contribute to introducing PAHs into the environment (Stout et al., 2001). Understanding the complicated pathways through which PAHs enter and circulate within the environment is vital for comprehending their impact on ecosystems and public health. PAHs have been identified as potent carcinogens and mutagens, capable of initiating genetic mutations and promoting cancer development in individuals subjected to prolonged or high-level exposures (Dieme et al., 2012; Jakovljević et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2016). Furthermore, PAHs are known to induce oxidative stress and inflammation in the human body, processes that are associated with a spectrum of health problems, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Agudelo-Castañeda et al., 2017; Cachon et al., 2014; Landkocz et al., 2017; Leclercq et al., 2016; Shahriyari et al., 2022). Understanding the pathways through which PAHs can impact human health is paramount, as it underscores the urgency of mitigating PAH emissions and reducing exposure levels.

Metals within PM constitute a noteworthy concern, given their significant presence and potential health implications. These metals encompass a range of elements and compounds arising from various natural and anthropogenic sources. Their appearance in PM particles results from processes such as industrial emissions, combustion of fossil fuels, and the resuspension of dust and soil particles (L. C. Chen & Lippmann, 2009; Wu et al., 2022). Exposure to PM-containing metals can profoundly and adversely affect human health. Some metals, including lead, cadmium, and nickel, are recognized neurotoxins capable of impairing cognitive development, particularly in children (L.-C. Chen et al., 2022). Additionally, certain metals, such as arsenic and chromium, possess carcinogenic properties and have been linked to an elevated risk of cancer among exposed populations (P. Pandey et al., 2013). These metals can also incite inflammation and oxidative stress upon inhalation, leading to respiratory symptoms and exacerbating conditions such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (MacNee & Donaldson, 2003; Zetlén et al., 2023). Furthermore, the translocation of metals from the lungs into the bloodstream raises concerns about potential cardiovascular effects, including an increased susceptibility to heart attacks and strokes (Guo et al., 2022). The mechanisms through which metals induce these health effects involve generating reactive oxygen species, disrupting enzyme function, and interfering with cellular processes (Valavanidis et al., 2008).

This paper discusses air pollution and public health protection by systematically investigating the following aims: understand the sources of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and metals within PM₁₀ fraction of particulate matter, quantify the relationships between PAHs and metals in PM₁₀ and gas consumption patterns, analyze the impact of meteorological conditions on the concentrations of PAHs and metals in the atmosphere, and understand interactions among gas consumption patterns, meteorological conditions, and the presence of PAHs and metals in PM₁₀ fraction of the particulate matter. To our knowledge, this study is the first that combines air quality data with meteorological and gas consumption data in the researched area. This investigation use an extensive dataset to understand the air pollution dynamics, with implications for environmental and public health outcomes, and therefore contribute to effective air quality management and public health protection by providing information about the sources and relationships of pollutants in the atmosphere.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area description

The study area for this research is the *Ksaverska cesta* measuring station (altitude 116 m a.s.l. 45°50'7" N, 15°58'42" E), located at the Institute for Medical Research and Occupational Health (IMROH), Zagreb, Croatia (Figure 1). The measuring station represents an urban residential area for pollution assessment. It is one of the six air pollution monitoring stations funded by the City of Zagreb and one of the oldest. Over the years, the IMROH has collected data on PAHs and metals at this station, systematically and continuously recording valuable information about air pollution daily. The station and surrounding area was previously described by Jakovljević et al. (2020). The Institute also acquired gas consumption data, providing essential information regarding energy consumption patterns. Combining air quality data from the *Ksaverska cesta* measuring station and meteorological and gas consumption data forms the foundation of this comprehensive investigation into the interplay between energy consumption, meteorological conditions, and the concentrations of PAHs and metals in the atmosphere.

From January 1st, 2017, to December 31st, 2020, 24-hour samples of particulate matter fraction PM₁₀ (PM with an equivalent aerodynamic diameter < 10 µm) were collected during the four years. Their content was determined, including metals arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), iron (Fe), copper (Cu), and zinc (Zn), following PAHs: benzo(a)pyrene (BaP), benzo(a)anthracene (BaA), benzo(ghi)perylene (BghiP), dibenzo(ah)anthracene (DahA), chrysene (Chry), benzo(k)fluoranthene (BkF), benzo(b)fluoranthene (BbF), benzo(j)fluoranthene (BjF), fluoranthene (Flu), and pyrene (Pyr). Simultaneously, nitrogen dioxide concentrations (NO₂) were also measured.

PM₁₀ samples were collected on quartz filters with low-volume samplers (Sven Leckel, ~55 m³/day). PAHs were extracted from filters in an ultrasonic bath using a solvent mixture of cyclohexane and toluene, centrifugated, evaporated to dryness, and redissolved in acetonitrile. The analysis used an Agilent Infinity 1260 HPLC system with a fluorescence detector. The detailed procedure was already described by Pehnec et al. (2016) and Jakovljević et al. (2020). For metal analysis, samples were microwave digested in nitric acid and analyzed using the inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) Agilent Technologies, model 7500cx (Beslic et al., 2020). In addition to the comprehensive data on metals and PAH concentrations within the PM₁₀ fraction, this study includes records of monthly gas consumption, average monthly temperature, pressure, precipitation, and wind speed over the same four-year period from 2017 to the end of 2020. The gas consumption data were obtained from the IMROH, which also operates the measurement station at *Ksaverska cesta*. This information is crucial for a better understanding of pollution concentration variations associated with heating seasonality and, more broadly, the elevated levels of pollutants during the winter period.

The meteorological data were obtained from the Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service (DHMZ) from a reference measuring station located within the research area, and this data was also used to understand seasonal oscillations in individual pollutants better.

Figure 1. Study area with air quality measuring station (*Ksaverska cesta*)

For subsequent statistical analysis, the data was prepared by calculating monthly means for each variable under consideration.

2.2. Statistical analysis

In this study, Python (version 3.10) with the libraries scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011), statsmodels (Seabold & Perktold, 2010) and seaborn (Waskom et al., 2017), served as the primary tool for the statistical analysis. Monthly means of the measured analytes were taken to facilitate an analysis since the gas consumption data are in a monthly frequency. The resulting dataset comprised 48 data points, representing each month during the four-year measurement period. A correlation matrix was constructed and analyzed to explore the interrelationships between variables. The correlation matrix provided insights into which variables exhibited significant correlations. This initial examination served as a foundation for further exploratory statistical techniques. Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) was employed to dissect the dataset further, providing valuable information about potential source contributions and temporal variations. This technique decomposed the data into non-negative components, enabling the identification of factors influencing the concentrations of PAHs and metals over the studied period and location. NMF is a dimensionality reduction technique that factorizes a non-negative data matrix into two non-negative matrices, often called the basis matrix and the coefficient matrix (Boutsidis & Gallopoulos, 2008; Marinetti et al., 2006). Mathematically, NMF can be represented as follows: given a non-negative data matrix X (with dimensions $m \times n$), NMF aims to find two non-negative matrices W (basis matrix) and H (coefficient matrix) such that $X \approx WH$ (Pauca et al., 2006). Moreover, the analysis was extended to linear regression modelling to deepen the understanding of the factors influencing pollutant concentrations. This step allowed the exploration of relationships within specific pollutant groups identified through NMF. Each NMF component was used as a dependent variable in separate regression models, with average air temperature, pressure, wind speed, precipitation, NO_2 , and gas consumption as independent variables (Deka et al., 2016). In the linear regression model, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) addressed the significant collinearity observed among average temperature, NO_2 , and gas consumption, as determined by Spearman's correlation heatmap (Figure 2). The application of PCA led to the derivation of principal components (PC1 and PC2), which were used in the regression model instead of the original collinear variables. Additionally, the model incorporated average monthly pressure (p_{avg}), precipitation, and wind speed as explanatory variables. This approach effectively reduces multicollinearity issues, improving the model's reliability and interpretability. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used as a dimensionality reduction technique, enabling a more transparent comprehension of how variables related to one another. PCA is a linear transformation technique that reduces the

dimensionality of a dataset while preserving as much of its variance as possible (Bro & Smilde, 2014). It identifies a set of orthogonal axes, known as principal components (PCs), which are linear combinations of the original variables. The mathematical representation of PCA provides a way to transform data into a new coordinate system that captures the most important variations in the data, making it easier to analyze while retaining much of the original information. Variables that displayed strong correlations or similar patterns of variation were found to cluster together in the PCA results (B. Pandey et al., 2014; Souza et al., 2018; Statheropoulos et al., 1998).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF)

The correlation matrix was calculated to summarize relationships among pollutant variables, helping to identify highly correlated pollutants and understand their behavior and common origins. Furthermore, heatmaps were made to visually represent the complex variable correlations within the dataset (Figure 2). The intercorrelation of pollutants was determined based on Pearson's correlations (Figure 2a), while Spearman's correlation was made between NO₂, meteorological parameters, and gas consumption (Figure 2b). There are several instances of strong positive correlations, colored by darker red, which may indicate common sources or similar environmental behaviors. Conversely, strong negative correlations, indicated by dark blue, imply an inverse relationship, hinting at distinct sources or divergent environmental processes for the variables. Figure 2a shows strong positive correlations among several pollutants, particularly between groups of PAHs such as BaA, Chry, BjF, BbF, BkF, DahA, BghiP, and BaP, indicating they might occur together. Zn also shows strong correlations within this group. Flu and Pyr show slightly less positive correlation compared to the other PAHs. Additionally, a notable cluster of strong correlations among heavy metals such as As, Cd, Pb, and Mn suggests these pollutants are likely to be found together in the same environments. Other elements, such as Fe and Cu, show moderate correlations with these clusters.

Figure 2. Heatmap illustrating pairwise correlations among dataset variables, with color intensity representing the strength and direction of associations for a) air pollutants and b) independent variables

NMF was used to understand the potential sources and the mutual relationships deeper, revealing temporal variability within the dataset. All pollutant variables were used in NMF analysis: BaP, BaA, BghiP, DahA, Chry, BkF, BbF, BjF, Flu, Pyr, As, Cd, Pb, Mn, Fe, Cu, and Zn. Notably, despite most PAHs exhibiting a high degree of positive intercorrelation and suggesting similar behavior, all were included to ensure a comprehensive assessment of the pollution sources.

The following sections are the outcomes of NMF, where the original data matrix was transformed into two new matrices, one representing the different sources of pollution and the other the contribution of each basis component to the observed data at each time point. This has given vectors that we refer to as NMF1 and NMF2 (Figure 3).

The time series graph (Figure 3a) shows the temporal profiles of three NMF factors, inspired by (Šimić et al., 2020), from the beginning of 2017 to the end of 2020. Each factor will likely represent a different combination or source of pollutants captured over the monthly averaged data. NMF1 shows significant variability over the observed period, with several peaks suggesting periodic increases in this factor value. NMF2 shows a less pronounced set of peaks than NMF1 but is represented with clear, high seasonality. Although NMF1 shows higher peaks in the colder part of the year (winter, autumn) compared to NMF2, it also shows some additional, smaller peaks in other seasons, suggesting the influence of other factors. The third NMF factor is relatively stable and flat, with minimal variation over time. This indicates that the variables of sources represented by NMF3 are consistent, with no significant changes or seasonal effects.

Figure 3. a) Time series graph for components NMF1, NMF2 and NMF3, b) bi-plot for NMF components

The NMF bi-plot was used to represent the source information within our dataset visually (Figure 3b). In this bi-plot, each variable is depicted as a vector, originating from the graph's origin. The angles between vectors convey the degree of association or dissociation between variables, illuminating the source dynamics and interrelationships. The length and direction of the vectors indicate the strength and nature of each pollutant's influence on the components, with longer vectors, such as those for Mn and Fe, suggesting a dominant influence on NMF2. This bi-plot identifies potential common sources for grouped pollutants and underscores the seasonal variance in pollutant levels. Variables that clustered closely in the bi-plot shared strong associations or exhibited analogous seasonal variations, while those with divergent orientations indicated relatively independent influences. NMF1 could include certain PAHs like Pyr, Flu, B_jF, Chry, and BaA, which may indicate more widespread sources.

Metals in ambient air may originate from various sources, such as industrial emissions, combustion of fossil fuels, traffic emissions mining, or agriculture (L. C. Chen & Lippmann, 2009; Soleimani et al., 2018). Mn, Fe, and Cu with long vectors pointing in a similar direction (Figure 3b) could be indicative of traffic emissions not related to combustion processes (which are also the source of PAHs), but those related to the wear of tires, brakes or other parts of the vehicles, or resuspension of road dust (Fu et al., 2023; Sternbeck et al., 2002; J. M. Wang et al., 2021). Mn, Fe, and Cu vectors suggest a strong influence on the data structure captured by NMF2. Other metals (Pb, Zn, Cd, and As) formed a separated cluster with shorter vectors and positions between axes of the NMF1 and NMF2 components and could be indicative of traffic emissions as well as high-temperature combustion (Furusjö et al., 2007; Sternbeck et al., 2002).

Other pollutants that cluster closer to the origin with shorter vectors, such as certain PAHs (Pyr, Flu, B_jF, Chry, BaA), may represent more diffuse or varied sources, such as residential heating (NMF1), which is also confirmed by the seasonality of NMF1. Especially Flu and Pyr are more related to the combustion of wood, grass, or coal (Jakovljević et al., 2015). Notably, coal has not been used in Croatia for decades, and heating in the study area mainly relies on gas or wood. However, neighboring countries (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, North Macedonia) still widely use coal

(Pehneć et al., 2020), contributing to cross-border air pollution, heavy industry emissions, and possibly sources of metal pollutants.

Other PAHs (DahA, BghiP, BaP, BbF, and BkF) have vector directions similar to those previously described PAHs. Still, pretty much the same length vectors can put them in a separate cluster with potentially a bit different pollution source, probably from vehicle exhaust emissions (combustion of gasoline in cars usually results in emissions of 5- and 6-ring PAHs) (Jakovljević et al., 2020). When comparing the findings of the present study with previous studies (Liu et al., 2021; X. Wang et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2006), there are parallels in the identification of pollution sources. While the current study suggests Mn, Fe, and Cu, as well as BghiP, DahA, BaP, BkF, and BbF, may be indicative of traffic emissions, Liu et al. (2021) also recognize a distinct factor associated with vehicle exhaust, marked by high molecular weight PAHs. Additionally, the clustering of NMF components in this study may resonate with Liu et al.'s factor related to coal combustion, attributed to moderate molecular weight PAHs. This underscores a commonality in source attribution across different analytical models and studies.

Pollutants that form a cluster, primarily composed of samples from the winter season, could indicate active or more prominent sources during colder weather, such as heating systems or reduced atmospheric dispersion (PAHs and partly As and Cd). Arsenic and cadmium are typical for high-temperature combustion emissions; compared with previous studies, these findings match source determination in other researched areas (Sternbeck et al., 2002).

3.2. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA was employed to address the significant collinearity observed among the predictors `temp_avg`, NO_2 and gas consumption (kWh), as determined by Spearman's correlation heatmap (Figure 2b). Sources of NO_2 are related to energy production and combustion of fossil fuels. In urban areas, NO_2 is usually a marker of traffic intensity (Šimić et al., 2020), and it is a typical product in vehicle exhausts (Carslaw, 2005; Kendrick et al., 2015).

A new heatmap was generated for further analysis to assess whether incorporating PC1 and PC2 effectively reduced multicollinearity among the variables (Figure 4a). In the subsequent linear regression analysis, the variables PC1 and PC2 were used, along with the average pressure, the wind speed, and the precipitation data. PC1 and PC2 captured 96.23% of the variance (90.03% from PC1 and 6.20% from PC2). This suggests that most of the variability in the data is represented by these two components. The time series plot for PCA components (Figure 4b) shows that PC1 reflects a seasonal cycle, where emissions driven by energy consumption typically rise when it gets colder. PC2 seems to capture specific conditions where NO_2 increases without a corresponding rise in energy use, suggesting influences beyond just temperature (possible traffic). Loadings are calculated to see how much each original variable contributes to the principal components. PC1 is heavily influenced by NO_2 (0.570), kWh (0.577), and `temp_avg` (-0.585), indicating that higher NO_2 and kWh values are associated with lower temperatures. PC2 is primarily influenced by NO_2 (0.786) and kWh (-0.591), with `temp_avg` (0.183) playing a minor role, suggesting that NO_2 increases independently of energy use, possibly due to traffic emissions. This interpretation aligns with the observed variance, where PC1 captures the general seasonal trend, and PC2 reflects conditions that specifically increase NO_2 levels without a corresponding rise in energy use. However, Figure 4a shows that PC2 strongly negatively correlates with wind speed and positively with pressure. This suggests that during winter, high-pressure systems (anticyclones) cause temperature inversions, trapping pollutants near the ground. Low wind speeds further exacerbate the situation, leading to higher concentrations of all pollutants in the air, indicating that such meteorological conditions could also cause pollution peaks. PC3 may be capturing noise or complex behaviors in the data that are not associated with clear trends or seasonal effects. This is the reason why it is not used in further analysis.

Figure 4. a) Spearman's rank correlation heatmap for PC1 and PC2 among other variables, b) time series graph for first three PCA components

3.3. Linear regression

Linear regression was used in data analyses to quantify the relationship between pollutants. Gas consumption (kWh), average temperature (temp_avg), and NO₂ were hence not used in the models directly because of the strong correlation (Figure 2). Regression analysis aimed to capture any observable trends or patterns in a multivariate space and consequently explain sources. Table 1 provides multiple linear regression models for three NMF factors (target variables), which were used as a dependent variable in separate regression models, with PC1, PC2, p_avg, precipitation, and wind as independent variables.

Table 1. Results of the multiple linear regression model for NMF1, NMF2 and NMF3 as a dependent variables and PC1, PC2, p_avg, wind and precipitation as a predictor

	Endpoint →	NMF1	NMF2	NMF3
	Model Parameter			
Model Statistics	R-squared	0.362	0.817	0.274
	F-statistic	4.771	37.54	3.165
	Prob (F-stat)	0.002	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-14}$	0.016
	No. observations	48	48	48
Coefficients	Constant	0.469	-4.588	0.236
	PC1	0.019	0.048	0.001
	PC2	0.164	-0.033	0.002
	p_avg	-0.001	0.005	-0.0002
	wind	0.036	-0.039	0.0003
	precipitation	-0.004	0.004	-0.003

The regression analysis reveals relationships between the latent environmental factors and each of the NMF components (NMF1, NMF2, and NMF3). For NMF1 (latent representation of Pyr, Flu, B_JF, Chry, BaA), the model explains 36.2% of the variability (R-squared = 0.362), indicating a relatively good fit. The adjusted R-squared is lower at 0.286, reflecting the model's predictive power after adjusting for the number of predictors. PC2 shows a positive and significant relationship with the dependent variable. However, the other variables, including PC1, do not significantly predict NMF1.

In contrast, the model for NMF2 (latent representation of Mn, Fe, Cu) demonstrates a robust fit, explaining 81.7% of the variability ($R^2 = 0.817$). The F-statistic is significant, suggesting the model is a good fit for the data. PC1 is a significant predictor with a positive coefficient, while PC2, precipitation, and wind are not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This could be because the metals in NMF2 are likely from the mechanical wear of vehicles. The high seasonality of PC1 could be linked to the seasonality of traffic density, with higher traffic density in winter. This interpretation aligns with findings by Rinkovec et al. (Rinkovec et al., 2018), where similar seasonal variations of platinum, palladium, and rhodium (originating from automotive catalytic converters) were observed at three locations in Zagreb. Therefore, the significant influence of PC1 on NMF2 may reflect the increased vehicle-related emissions during winter months. In the case of NMF3, the model exhibits a limited explanatory power similar to NMF1 ($R^2 = 0.274$). PC1 shows a significant positive impact, but other variables, including PC2, are not statistically significant.

The results indicate that while NMF2 is strongly influenced by the seasonal changes represented by PC1, which captures temperature and gas consumption, the variability in NMF1 and NMF3 is less clearly explained by the variables included in the analysis. NMF2, representing metals likely from vehicle wear, aligns with the high traffic density in winter, as reflected in PC1. NMF1 shows a positive relationship with PC2, which can be explained by traffic emissions, as NO_2 is a major component of PC2. However, this connection might be more complex, as NMF1 represents PAHs typically from biomass burning, suggesting that other factors might also be significant. NMF3 shows a relationship to PC1 similar to that of NMF2, indicating that seasonal variations in temperature and gas consumption influence both NMF2 and NMF3, although NMF3's specific sources remain less clear. This suggests that while NMF1 and NMF3 share a similar relationship with PC1, the factors influencing NMF1 are more varied and complex.

The integration of PCA and NMF methodologies combined with linear regression has facilitated a better understanding of pollution sources. Metals such as Mn, Fe, and Cu, identified through NMF2 with longer vectors, seem to be connected to traffic emissions but probably not in the context of fuel combustion. PAHs present a diverse picture: while compounds like Pyr and Flu cluster near the origin, indicating sources such as residential heating, others such as BghiP and BaP are consistent with vehicular emissions, as denoted by their vector lengths and directions. This analysis helps in understanding the interactions of pollutants, revealing source contributions of pollution in the urban environment.

4. Conclusions

This study, located around the Ksaverska cesta air quality measuring station in Zagreb, provides valuable insights into the relationship between gas consumption, meteorological conditions, and the concentrations of PAHs and metals in the atmosphere. This research combines air quality data with meteorological and gas consumption data, offering a better understanding of the factors influencing pollution dynamics in the specified study region by integrating NMF with regression models.

In conclusion, this study not only contributes to understanding the dynamics influencing air quality in the Zagreb area but also emphasizes the need for a multidimensional approach to capture the diverse factors affecting pollutant concentrations. The integration of air quality, meteorological, and gas consumption data offers a robust foundation for further research and policy-making, with potential implications for environmental and public health outcomes. Future work may include fine-tuning these analyses with additional variables and measuring stations or alternate statistical methods to improve understanding of this complex ecological system further.

Statements & Declarations

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author Contributions

Study conception and design: Nikolina Račić, Mario Lovrić, Stanko Ružičić. Data analysis: Nikolina Račić, Mario Lovrić, Teo Terzić. Laboratory analysis were performed by Ivana Jakovljević, Zdravka Sever Štrukil, Jamina Rinkovec and Silva Žužul. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Nikolina Račić. Manuscript revision: Gordana Pehnec, Mario Lovrić, Stanko Ružičić. All authors approved the submitted version.

Data Availability

Supporting data may be obtained from the website: <http://iszz.azo.hr/iskzl/>, either through the query on the website or by the written request.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Since this study did not collect personal information, no ethical approval was required.

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